

NEW METHODS OF TEACHING ANATOMY

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Abstract: the article deals with new methodologies for teaching human anatomy using color photos of natural anatomical specimens. About the need for podgotovki for publication by anatomical atlases of a new type of photographic atlases of anatomical specimens, to establish banks of these photos and use them for demonstrations on monitors in the training of the anatomical rooms.

Keywords: anatomical, anatomical structure, multi-color drawings, pictures of anatomical structures.

Recently, the provision of many anatomical departments with anatomical specimens has been reduced to a minimum. If the departments still have anatomical specimens from the distant past, they resemble Egyptian mummies in appearance, consistency and color more than educational anatomical specimens. In most medical universities, even specimens from anatomical museums have been “buried”. How can one learn the basics of human anatomy in such conditions?

Young anatomists do not know how to dissect – they had nothing to learn from, since the supply of abandoned corpses was stopped in the 90s. How can one teach students then?

At present, there are plenty of anatomical textbooks and atlases, which are a necessary component of the educational process, especially if the drawings are multi-colored, with red arteries, blue veins and yellow nerves. But these structures inside the human body do not look like that, and very often they look completely different, not like in the colorful pictures in the atlases. Atlases have high printing quality, but they do not demonstrate the true structures of the human body. Students and young doctors do not recognize the anatomical structures of the human body on monitors during endoscopic examinations; they did not see them when studying anatomy, they only saw drawings [1].

A look at new editions of anatomical textbooks and atlases from the end of the 20th century shows that they are full of “lightweight”, “minimally simplified” colorful color illustrations taken from previously published editions, often without indicating the source. The price of such weighty editions has jumped considerably, so that young colleagues’ anatomists and clinicians “cannot afford” them.

Many anatomical editions have sharply turned towards the clinic, physiology, decorating them with colorful graphic and color drawings, without showing the true structures of the human body. Some anatomical atlases are full of clinical terms and concepts that are still unclear to students not only in their first, but also in their second year of study at a medical university. Some atlases are filled with terms in Russian, Latin and English, sometimes their number reaches 40 per page. Naturally, such an atlas is much more expensive, because it is also an English textbook, and the weight of one volume exceeds three kilograms.

There is no point in waiting for anatomical departments to be supplied with educational anatomical specimens in the next 5-6 years. Many old-school anatomists have left or are retiring, and young teachers still need to learn how to work with anatomical material, and that is only if they receive it.

Based on this, the development of educational anatomical material is again in the center of attention of professional anatomists, and interest in this has never been as high as it is now. Computer technologies, including “virtual three-dimensional images” (although they look like plastic robots), as well as professional artists are involved in this.

It is known that the practical skills of doctors in carrying out medical manipulations and research are based primarily on recognizing the anatomical structures of the body, and secondarily on the acquired anatomical knowledge of the shape and topography of structures in a certain anatomical region.

Therefore, it is very important that a future doctor begins his professional education as early as possible with real images of real anatomical structures, so that they become familiar and habitual to him in shape and position [2].

Currently, medical education as a whole does not correspond to this, since, practically, anatomical preparations have disappeared from teaching, and the existing anatomical atlases are full of colorful pictures of the anatomical structures of the human body, which you will not see in the body of a living person. Without high-quality true color rendition of the anatomical structures of the human body while preserving their shape and position, it is impossible to study the human body.

Based on the above and taking into account the lack of natural educational anatomical preparations, we propose a new methodology for teaching human anatomy using color photographs of natural anatomical preparations. First of all, it is necessary to prepare for publication anatomical atlases of a new type - photographic atlases of anatomical preparations, then - on all kinds of digital media to create banks of these photographs and use them for demonstrations on monitors in educational anatomical rooms. The task is not to write a new anatomy textbook (there are enough of them written), not to replace them, but to supplement them with a new type of visual aid [3]. Thus, we hope that this can close the anatomical gap between the existing anatomical atlases and practical reality in the absence of educational anatomical preparations. The eye, as a real fixator, is able to remember the shape, size, color and position of anatomical structures. A student studies anatomy, or a surgeon operates, or a doctor examines a patient, they always deal with only one small area, and all this can be presented in photographs of natural preparations, where the anatomical structures look like on the human body.

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